

IMPACT OF WOMEN ENTREPRENEURSHIP ON DIGITAL ENTREPRENEURSHIP: A FOCUS ON WOMEN'S PARTICIPATION IN BANGLADESH

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Abstract

This research article investigates the impact of women entrepreneurship on digital entrepreneurship in Bangladesh, aiming to analyze the role of women in the evolving digital landscape. The study identifies critical challenges faced by women entrepreneurs in accessing digital opportunities, assesses the current state of digital entrepreneurship, and examines the facilitators and barriers to women's participation. Utilizing a mixed-methods approach, the study incorporates quantitative data from a survey of 50 women entrepreneurs, predominantly from Dhaka, Narayanganj, and Gazipur, alongside qualitative insights from in-depth interviews. Key findings reveal significant obstacles such as limited access to finance, insufficient training, and cultural constraints that hinder women's entrepreneurial ventures. Despite an increase in women-led businesses, only 7.2% of enterprises in Bangladesh are owned by women, with a concentration in sectors like handicrafts and garments. The study underscores the need for targeted strategies to enhance women's engagement in digital entrepreneurship, including improved access to financial resources, tailored training programs, and supportive policies. By addressing the multifaceted challenges identified, this research aims to contribute to the economic empowerment of women in Bangladesh, ultimately fostering greater participation in the digital economy and promoting sustainable development.

Keywords: Entrepreneurship, Digital Entrepreneurship, Women Entrepreneurship, Digital Opportunity, Women Participation.

1. INTRODUCTION

Digital entrepreneurship has emerged as a significant contributor to the economic growth of many countries. In Bangladesh, digital entrepreneurship has shown remarkable growth in the last few years. According to Akther and Parvin, "Women entrepreneurs in Bangladesh represent a large group of women who are exploring new panoramas of economic participation". However, there is still a significant gender gap in entrepreneurship, with women entrepreneurs facing many challenges in accessing resources, networks, and funding. This gender gap in entrepreneurship is even more pronounced in digital entrepreneurship. Therefore, it is essential to understand the factors that influence women's participation in digital entrepreneurship in Bangladesh. In the 21st century we are living in the digital world which results tremendous change in businesses enterprise that digitally leaving back the traditional way. In other words, digitization has been transforming the way of doing businesses. It brings the businesses back to the door-step of customers, suppliers and others stakeholders affecting businesses elsewhere

(Aftab & Mahmood, 2014, p. 99-100). When we talk about the term entrepreneurship, we refer to people that act upon opportunities and ideas and transform them into something that has value for other people. The value that is created can be cultural, social or financial. While, the term digital entrepreneurship alludes in a subcategory of business enterprise that a few or all of the business processes, used to be physical and were run in a traditional way but not all have been digitalized. Schumpeter (1934) described entrepreneur as the innovator who introduces something new into an economy and Kirzner (1997) stressed the fact that the entrepreneur is the decision maker in a particular cultural context, who commands a range of behaviors that exploit these opportunities (cited in Afroze & others, 2014, p.29). Garga and Bagga (2009) defined women entrepreneurship as the women or a group of women who initiate, organize and operate a business enterprise. Female-owned innovations and business are one of the most important and fast-growing aspects of entrepreneurship worldwide (Brush & Cooper, 2012). Consequently, Nambisan (2016) argued that digital technologies have made entrepreneurship unbounded in terms of process and outcome. Similarly, other researchers argue that entrepreneurs involved in digital innovation keep the innovation always intentionally incomplete and remain in a state of flux for further scale and scope of innovation (Kallinikos et al., 2013; Lyytinen et al., 2016) cited in Huque 2017, p.3-4. Thus, Women entrepreneurs must possess sound knowledge about the technological advancements and how they will apply these in their business within their ability.

2. STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Existing sex ratio in demographic structure of Bangladesh indicates that women comprise more than 50%. According to the Bangladesh Bureau of Statistics there are 98m males per 100 females (BBS, Preliminary Report on Population and Housing Census 2022, p.8). But the natural tendency of Bangladeshi women is to stay at home. Whereas digital entrepreneurship allows the female entrepreneurs to do business works mostly from their home. A notable characteristic of emerging markets is that those markets are highly unstable and unpredictable because of their rapidly changing economy. However, Szerb and others in 2021 asserts that “What has happened in the 21st century with the reemergence of autonomous networks is that the balance between the state and the market shifted as the hierarchy was replaced by networks”. But Huq M. S identified that access to marketing information is a problem of women entrepreneurs. They do not know how to get access to domestic as well as export market. Even after selling their products on account, another difficulty arises in collecting those accounts receivables.

Women entrepreneurs are amongst the fastest-growing entrepreneurial population in the world (Cardella, Sanchez & Garcia 2020). Despite their growing importance, there is still a lack of research on women entrepreneurship, particularly in emerging economies (Elliott & Mavriplis 2020). According to McClelland et al. (2005), female entrepreneurship is an under-researched field of immense business opportunities and requires special attention. Zhu, Kara, and Zhu (2019) agreed that very limited research has been done focusing on female entrepreneurs. In addition, there is very little research on the internationalization of women entrepreneurial firms from emerging markets particularly those from

Bangladesh (Ferdous B & Tanya S.; 2021). Further, it is important to study the impact of women entrepreneurship on digital entrepreneurship because it is a new concept in Bangladeshi business arena.

3. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

3.1 General objective:

The overall aim of this research is to explore and analyze the role of women entrepreneurship in the context of Bangladesh on the entrepreneurship that depends on digitalization.

3.2 Specific Objectives:

1. To identify the challenges faced by women entrepreneurs in accessing digital entrepreneurship opportunities in Bangladesh.
2. To analyze the current status of digital entrepreneurship in Bangladesh.
3. To explore the factors that facilitates or hinders women's participation in digital entrepreneurship in Bangladesh.
4. To examine the impact of women entrepreneurship on digital entrepreneurship in Bangladesh.
5. To suggest strategies to improve women's participation in digital entrepreneurship in Bangladesh.

4. RESEARCH QUESTIONS

The research questions that directed this research are:

1. What are the challenges that the women entrepreneurs face to access in digitalization arena?
2. To What extent the women entrepreneurs in Bangladesh are incorporated with the digitalization?
3. What are the factors affects women entrepreneurs' participation in digital entrepreneurship?
4. What is the impact of women entrepreneurship on digital entrepreneurship in Bangladesh?
5. What are the strategies needs to enhance women entrepreneurs' participation in digital entrepreneurship.

5. METHODOLOGY

5.1 Research approach and design:

The researchers have used mixed-methods approach in this study. Firstly, a survey has been conducted to gather quantitative data on the challenges faced by women

entrepreneurs in accessing digital entrepreneurship opportunities. Secondly, qualitative data have been collected through in-depth interviews with women entrepreneurs and digital entrepreneurs in Bangladesh. Finally, the data have been analyzed using statistical tools and thematic analysis to identify the factors that influence women's participation in digital entrepreneurship.

5.2 Sample size and data collection procedure:

In this research, all over Bangladesh is the sampling unit. What is notable is that most of the women entrepreneurs are in the Dhaka division and particularly in three districts which are Dhaka, Narayangonj and Gazipur. Therefore, more samples have been collected from the Dhaka division. All the women entrepreneurs of Bangladesh who normally perform their business activities digitally constitute the population of this research. A total of 50 women entrepreneurs is the sample size of the study. A stratified random sampling technique has been applied for this study. The study has considered both primary and secondary data. The Primary data have been collected through interviews. The researchers conducted each interview session individually in order to obtain accurate information in the case of the beneficiaries. Secondary data have been collected from various published materials such as research articles, monographs, Bangladesh Bureau of Statistics and Bangladesh Ministry of Commerce.

5.3 Data analysis technique:

The data have been organized and analyzed after collection. As mixed method has been used to analyze the collected data, thematic interpretation has been done first, then frequency tables have been drawn. The open-ended questions were analyzed thematically (Creswell, 2008) these are qualitative in nature so these have been transcribed and analyzed comparatively irrespective on the economical context of the union.

6. FEMALE ENTREPRENEURSHIP AND DIGITALIZATION

The rise of female entrepreneurship in the digital age is being influenced by advancements in technology. These developments are reshaping the landscape for entrepreneurs by providing new tools and opportunities for startups (Dholakia and Kshetri 2004; Khajeheian 2013). Digital technologies are recognized as pivotal in transforming the entrepreneurial environment, acting as catalysts that enable the creation of new ventures (Bi et al. 2017; Giones and Brem 2017). They have fundamentally altered work dynamics and business practices, impacting how entrepreneurs operate (Autio et al. 2018; Sussan and Acs 2017). While the internet has been acknowledged as a powerful platform for launching and enhancing ventures, research is only beginning to explore how digital technologies shape entrepreneurial ecosystems (Sussan and Acs 2017). Gender disparities in accessing entrepreneurial opportunities and how digitalization might alleviate these inequalities are pressing topics of debate. Additionally, there's growing interest in understanding how digital tools can empower women and potentially disrupt traditional gender roles (Dy et al. 2018; Wajcman 2010, p. 144).

Previous research in cyber feminism has examined women's attitudes toward digital technology, emphasizing how the Internet's disruptive capabilities can lower barriers to entry for women in entrepreneurship, a field traditionally dominated by men (Dy et al. 2018; Martin and Wright 2005). Women stand to gain from digital advancements through enhanced work flexibility and reduced constraints on mobility. Digital platforms facilitate their access to new knowledge and opportunities, such as crowd funding, thereby empowering them in business endeavors (Rosser 2005). However, the actual benefits of digital technology for women may not fully materialize in environments where gender disparities persist in terms of access, skills, and confidence with digital technologies (Daniels 2009; Dy et al. 2018). Cyber feminist research argues that inequalities offline are mirrored in online spaces (Ughetto, E., Rossi, M., Audretsch, D. et al. 2020)

Meta reports that over 52 million Facebook pages have been created in Bangladesh, with women owning about 40% of them. This translates to over 20 million Facebook pages owned by women in the country. The World Bank indicates that women entrepreneurs represent just 7.2% of businesses in Bangladesh, though this number is on the rise. In 2018, the number of women-owned businesses grew by 12%. Most women entrepreneurs in Bangladesh run micro-enterprises, which generally have fewer than five employees and generate less than \$10,000 in annual revenue. The predominant sectors for these women-owned businesses include fashion, food and beverage, retail, garment, jute, and leather industries.

7. FINDINGS AND ANALYSIS

The research on women digital entrepreneurship is insufficient, scattered, and lacking in practical insights. Additionally, most studies in this field appear in non-specialized journals. There is a shortage of research examining the impact of gender and cross-country comparisons. The existing literature lacks a variety of epistemological and methodological approaches. Theoretical connections across different areas of female entrepreneurship research are weak, making this field challenging for scholars. Few researchers specialize deeply in this topic, with most contributing either to digital entrepreneurship or female entrepreneurship, but not both.

Bangladesh, a swiftly developing nation, stands to benefit significantly from integrating women into the business sphere. Women's participation in the economy and their control over productive resources accelerate development, alleviate poverty, reduce inequalities, and enhance children's nutrition, health, and school attendance. Women are more likely than men to reinvest their earnings into their families and communities, fostering local economic growth. In recent years, the rate of women starting businesses in Bangladesh has increased notably. Nonetheless, women still own and manage fewer businesses compared to men. The Economic Census 2013 reported 0.56 million (7.21%) female-headed establishments, up from 0.10 million (2.80%) in 2001 and 2003. The rising rate and the characteristics, motivations, success rates, and gender-related uniqueness of female entrepreneurs are complex and varied.

Historically, fewer women than men have ventured into entrepreneurship. Various factors explain the gender differences in entrepreneurial behavior, which have significant macroeconomic implications. Cultural reasons, such as discrimination, influence women's propensity to start businesses differently than men. In developing countries like Bangladesh, the rates of female entrepreneurship are increasing because women face higher barriers to formal employment and often turn to entrepreneurship to escape unemployment and poverty. Research shows that women face unfavorable opportunities and incentives to start businesses despite their capabilities and knowledge.

Gender gaps in start-up activities are wider in wealthier regions and narrower in poorer regions, where many women start businesses out of necessity. Women in poorer regions tend to be more confident in their entrepreneurial abilities and less afraid of failure compared to women in better-off regions. The entry of women into entrepreneurship results from a complex interplay of constraints and opportunities, along with external motivations and aspirations. The services sector is particularly attractive to women due to their knowledge and experience, and the lower capital requirements compared to manufacturing and high-tech sectors. Women often rely on extended families for social support, which can influence their entrepreneurial decisions.

Female entrepreneurs typically have lower growth expectations, and their firms tend to grow more slowly in terms of sales and employment compared to those owned by men. Some evidence suggests that women prioritize business survival over growth, leading them to become portfolio entrepreneurs rather than serial entrepreneurs. Female entrepreneurs are diverse, coming from various backgrounds with different growth aspirations and enterprise sizes. They often use personal resources and borrow from friends and family to start businesses, valuing networking as a key success factor. Women generally have different management styles, often following the relational theory of management, which emphasizes building relationships and motivating employees through influence and communication. This approach can make women more competitive in business.

Access to adequate capital remains a significant obstacle for female entrepreneurs, who often start businesses with limited capital. Balancing work and family responsibilities makes entrepreneurship more appealing than traditional employment for some women, despite the long hours it may require. Traditional societal roles and well-established male networks pose additional challenges for women in business. Discrimination and societal perceptions about women's roles can hinder their success as entrepreneurs. The motivation to start a business among women is influenced by both 'push' factors (negative forces like job loss and unemployment) and 'pull' factors (positive forces like the desire for independence and personal fulfillment). Research indicates women start businesses for autonomy, security, and satisfaction, often due to past workplace discrimination or personal circumstances.

Supporting female entrepreneurship involves addressing overarching financial inclusion issues alongside specific gender-related challenges. Women in Bangladesh have less access to finance, resources, services, and opportunities, which hampers their ability to

participate in socioeconomic development. Many women operate in the informal sector and face difficulties in accessing finance, land, managerial skills, and business development training. Women's restricted movement, high workloads, unpaid labor, and lack of decision-making power at home keep them in disadvantaged positions. Economic empowerment is crucial for achieving gender equality and improving living standards. Supporting micro and small enterprise development can significantly benefit women entrepreneurs. Discrimination against women, rooted in cultural and societal gender beliefs, contributes to the gender gap in entrepreneurship in Bangladesh. This reduces women's likelihood of becoming entrepreneurs and their potential earnings and benefits from entrepreneurship. Women in Bangladesh can drive significant change in households and communities when given opportunities. To enhance the contribution of female entrepreneurship to development, achieving gender equality and fairness is essential.

Only 7.2% of businesses in Bangladesh are owned by women. According to data from the Bangladesh Bureau of Statistics (BBS), there were 2.8% million female-owned SMEs in Bangladesh in 2020, or about 24.6% of all SMEs in the nation. As Ahmmand and Haq (2013) says Women participation in entrepreneurship began to rise after the liberation in 1996, reaching its peak between 2000 and 2005. However, it declined thereafter due to various challenges faced by women entrepreneurs.

According to a survey of 50 women entrepreneurs, 63 percent are primarily involved in handicrafts, followed by 17 percent in garment businesses, and 7 percent in beauty parlors. The remaining 13 percent is distributed among food services (5%), agro-based ventures (3%), printing (1%), information technology (2%), and other sectors (2%).

7.1 Problems Faced By Women Entrepreneurs

Access to Finance & Financial Institutions: Women entrepreneurs in Bangladesh struggle significantly with financial access, primarily due to inadequate initial capital. Haq (as cited in Sinha, 2005) points out that they receive under 10% of commercial credit, often facing traditional biases and a lack of collateral. Gender-based obstacles such as traditional beliefs, cultural and social values, and lack of collateral further complicate the situation for women. Additional hindrances include high transaction costs, rigid collateral requirements, and extensive paperwork (Charumathi et al., 1998). These factors, along with high interest rates (Sinha, 2005, p.15), lack of experience and information, lower investment, and inadequate facilities like business premises or equipment, often impede the growth and sustainability of enterprises led by women.

Lack of Knowledge: A key challenge for women entrepreneurs in Bangladesh is their limited knowledge, as many have not progressed beyond the eighth grade or SSC level. Understanding essential business concepts such as operations, management, and economics is crucial for success in today's market. Islam and Aktaruzzaman (2001) finds that 76.3% of rural entrepreneurs lack formal education, with nearly 17% completely illiterate and 59.3% only able to sign their names. Additionally, 72% of respondents strongly agreed and 20% agreed that this lack of knowledge significantly hampers women's entrepreneurship.

Lack of Training: In Bangladesh, many rural women are uneducated and impoverished, lacking protections against insecurity and illiteracy. Rahman (2010) notes that societal barriers prevent them from accessing vocational and technical training. A USAID study (2011) finds that female entrepreneurs often face discrimination and limited opportunities from men, hindering their skill development. MIDAS (2009) reports that without essential education, training, and social security, women struggle to establish enterprises. Women represent less than 13% of trainees in enterprise development programs (Finnegan, cited in Sinha, 2005), and Bangladesh ranks second lowest among South Asian countries for female enrollment in secondary vocational education (Haq, cited in Sinha, 2005). Surveys indicate that 80% of respondents view inadequate training facilities as a major barrier, leaving women entrepreneurs at a significant disadvantage.

Lack of Entrepreneurial Training: While entrepreneurial training is essential, it is mostly available in urban areas, disadvantaging rural women. Rahman, Hossain, and Miah (2000) argues that without adequate training facilities, women cannot effectively utilize available resources. Only 8% of rural women entrepreneurs have received relevant training, and nearly 78% possess less than three years of experience, largely due to societal norms that restrict their opportunities.

Family Responsibilities: Family obligations, such as household chores and childcare, hinder women from acquiring skills and knowledge, as they often lack the time to improve their proficiency. In contrast, male entrepreneurs typically do not face this burden, which reduces women's capacity for constructive learning and diminishes their motivation to utilize their resources effectively. These distractions contribute to deficiencies in managerial skills and strategic planning, crucial for entrepreneurial success. A survey indicates that 70% of respondents strongly agreed and 30% agreed that family responsibilities significantly obstruct women's entrepreneurship, with no respondents expressing indifference or disagreement.

Government's Taxing Policy: Tax policies in Bangladesh greatly affect the growth of women entrepreneurship. Many tax regulations are too complex for average income earners to navigate, with requirements for TIN Certificates, tax credits, and trade licenses adding to the challenges. Increases in tax rates, new taxes or VAT, and a lack of tax holidays further stifle growth. In a survey, 40% of respondents strongly agreed that government tax policies hinder women entrepreneurs, while 34% agreed, 10% were indifferent, and 16% disagreed.

Lack of Skilled/Trained Manpower: The shortage of skilled and trained workers is another significant barrier for women entrepreneurs. Successful businesses need capable employees who can enhance productivity and quality while reducing costs (Abdin, 2010). Unfortunately, few agencies in Bangladesh train individuals adequately for entrepreneurship. A survey revealed that 78% of respondents strongly agreed that the lack of skilled workers is a major obstacle, while 20% agreed, 2% were indifferent, and 2% disagreed.

Access to Marketing Facility: Access to marketing facilities poses a significant barrier to the growth of women entrepreneurs, with 88% of respondents strongly agreeing and 10% agreeing that it is a major issue. Only 2% were indifferent, and none disagreed. Effective marketing is essential for products and services offered by women in micro, small, and medium enterprises (SMEs). Factors such as expertise, understanding, and experience play a crucial role in accessing these marketing facilities. Sinha (2005) highlights that women often encounter substantial challenges in running their SMEs due to market access difficulties. Rahman (2010, p. 12) notes that despite many women having strong marketing skills, social restrictions and violence hinder their ability to secure contracts with local and international markets. Furthermore, rural women entrepreneurs face additional challenges in entering contracts.

Access to Marketing Information and Networks: Women entrepreneurs struggle to connect with trade and industry due to a lack of marketing information, with 74% of respondents citing it as a major issue. Many women lack the knowledge to enter domestic and export markets and face barriers in existing male-dominated networks. Although women operate about 50% of SMEs, few are recognized as business professionals. Initiatives like those from the Bangladesh Federation of Chamber of Commerce and Industries (FBCCI) have not effectively promoted female entrepreneurship.

Lack of Access to Policymakers: Female entrepreneurs face significant barriers in accessing policymakers, which restricts their ability to engage in meaningful policymaking. Male entrepreneurs typically have more influence and better access to decision-makers, making it harder for women to enter leadership roles.

Lack of Access to Infrastructure: Inadequate infrastructure, particularly in rural areas, poses a major challenge, with 88% of respondents agreeing it hinders women's entrepreneurship. Essential services like electricity and gas are often lacking, impacting the growth of women-led SMEs. The government needs to prioritize infrastructure development to support these businesses.

Lack of Access to Technology: Women entrepreneurs often rely on outdated local technologies, limiting their competitiveness. Studies show that women have less access to technological innovations, resulting in low-quality production and income losses. A significant 68% of respondents identified inadequate access to modern technology as a major barrier to women's entrepreneurial development.

Absence of R&D: A significant challenge for women entrepreneurs is the lack of investment in research and development (R&D). R&D is vital for enhancing product quality and fostering innovation. In Bangladesh, many women in micro, small, and medium enterprises (SMEs) find it financially difficult to invest in R&D, limiting their ability to improve or develop new products and hindering their competitiveness in local and global markets. Survey data shows that 28% of respondents strongly agreed and 50% agreed that the absence of R&D is a major barrier, while 10% were indifferent, and 12% disagreed.

Insufficient Guidance from Government and NGOs: Another obstacle is the inadequate guidance from both the government and NGOs. Despite various efforts, the lack of clear guidelines hampers the growth of women entrepreneurs in SMEs. Survey results reveal that 53% strongly agreed and 34% agreed that insufficient guidance is a challenge, with 6% indifferent and 6% disagreeing.

Lack of Support Services: Women entrepreneurs in rural Bangladesh often lack access to essential cooperative and support services, creating social, cultural, and economic barriers that negatively impact product quality and income, as noted in a UNDP study (REOPA-CST, 2007).

Lack of Land Use Rights: A significant obstacle for women entrepreneurs is the difficulty in accessing land for business use. Village women face challenges in obtaining land, which is crucial for developing rural entrepreneurship.

Problems in Collecting Accounts Receivable: Women entrepreneurs also struggle with collecting accounts receivable after selling on credit. Many are unfamiliar with credit terms and payment processes, which reduces profitability. According to survey data, 68% strongly agreed and 24% agreed that this issue hampers their growth, while 4% were indifferent, and 4% disagreed.

8. RECOMMENDATIONS

- After analyzing the findings, several recommendations are proposed to overcome the barriers faced by women entrepreneurship in Bangladesh:
- The government, followed by NGOs and SMEF, should address the financing needs of women entrepreneurs, as financing remains a major obstacle. Steps should be taken to increase access to financing through state-owned banks at lower interest rates, and special financial packages tailored for women entrepreneurs in both urban and rural areas should be introduced. NGOs, MIDAS, and SMEF should enhance their efforts in disbursing loans with flexible terms. Private commercial banks could also offer special financing packages for women entrepreneurs, potentially alleviating the financing problem.
- Lengthy and complex loan application procedures should be simplified by financial institutions, both public and private, including micro-credit organizations, MIDAS, and SMEF, to encourage women entrepreneurs, particularly newcomers.
- Despite women's significant involvement in various SMEs, their entrepreneurial potential has not been adequately developed, according to Chowdhury (2007, p.241). Governments and NGOs in Bangladesh should continue issuing policy guidelines to promote the growth of micro, SMEs, and large enterprises led by women.
- Entrepreneurship courses should be introduced in formal and informal educational institutions across Bangladesh to inspire underprivileged women to consider entrepreneurship as a means of creating jobs rather than just seeking employment. This initiative would enhance their entrepreneurial skills, knowledge, and confidence.

- Private sector and NGOs should provide business management and risk assessment training to women entrepreneurs to improve their business acumen and operational efficiency. Educated entrepreneurs can confidently assume entrepreneurial responsibilities, take calculated risks, and access crucial information about entrepreneurial activities.
- Practical and needs-based training programs should be developed specifically for entrepreneurs to equip them with practical knowledge applicable to their businesses. Organizations like SMEF and BWCCI, already active in supporting women entrepreneurship, should expand their offerings to include more practical training facilities.
- Addressing the shortage of skilled manpower is crucial. NGOs, SMEF, and the government should collaborate to train and develop skilled professionals who can support the expansion of women entrepreneurship.
- Governments should ensure the provision of essential utilities and infrastructure such as gas, electricity, and other facilities to facilitate the growth of women entrepreneurship, as these factors currently pose significant barriers.
- Marketing products produced by women entrepreneurs remains a challenge. They should be equipped with knowledge of different marketing strategies. Private enterprises and NGOs can act as intermediaries by purchasing products in bulk and distributing them across various markets. Trade fairs can also be organized to showcase and sell their products, easing the burden of marketing.
- Providing sufficient information about international markets, marketing opportunities, economic conditions, and market predictions can empower women entrepreneurs to strategize effectively for their products.
- Women entrepreneurs should be knowledgeable about and adept at utilizing the latest technological advancements to expand their businesses. Access to computers and the internet can help them explore new markets and connect with potential buyers worldwide, enhancing their business prospects beyond local boundaries.
- Government fiscal, industrial, and monetary policies directly impact business operations. Stable policies that do not frequently change can provide a conducive environment for women entrepreneurs to grow and expand their businesses without undue hindrances.
- The National Board of Revenue (NBR) could consider extending tax holiday benefits to women entrepreneurs and offering special incentives such as tax rebates or initial tax exemptions for newly established businesses led by women.
- Improving product quality is crucial in today's competitive business environment. Women entrepreneurs should prioritize research and development (R&D) to enhance product quality and to innovate new products, thereby staying competitive in the market.

Table 1: Sector Wise Participations of Women Enterprise in Business

Sector	Enterprises
Handicraft	63%
Garment	17%
Parlor	7%
Food	5%
Agro based	3%
Printing	1%
ICT	2%
Others	2%

Source: Personal data collection

9. RESEARCH LIMITATIONS/IMPLICATIONS

This SLR research aims to provide an overview of the female DE field by identifying the current trend of research and recognizing future research directions and to improve readers' knowledge of this research branch.

10. PRACTICAL IMPLICATIONS

This review has classified the field's main topics and found that the influence of context (institutional and social) is the most investigated issue. Further, it presents a potential for practitioners' contribution to the field as coauthors and outlines needed studies.

11. ORIGINALITY/VALUE

This study provides a comprehensive, cross-disciplinary, updated review and research agenda that supplements rather than substitutes the existing literature reviews on female entrepreneurship. Moreover, this study makes a significant contribution by presenting the stages of development in female DE research within the context of the overall literature on female entrepreneurship.

12. CONCLUSION

This study highlights the critical role of women entrepreneurs in enhancing digital entrepreneurship in Bangladesh. The findings reveal significant challenges faced by women, including limited access to finance, lack of training, and societal constraints, which hinder their participation in digital markets. Despite these barriers, the increasing number of women entering entrepreneurship presents a valuable opportunity for growth and development of economy. By addressing the systemic issues and providing targeted support, such as improved access to resources, training, and infrastructure, Bangladesh can enhance women's contributions to the digital economy. Furthermore, fostering a supportive environment for women entrepreneurs can lead to broader socio-economic benefits, reducing inequalities and improving community well-being. This study underscores the necessity for collaborative efforts from government, NGOs, and private sectors to create an inclusive framework that empowers women and enables them to thrive in the digital entrepreneurship landscape. Ultimately, promoting women's

entrepreneurship is essential for achieving sustainable development and economic progress in Bangladesh.

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